

The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part Three: Legal Affairs

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Abstract:

In 1867, Patrick Moloney was one of the first two graduates from an Australian Medical School. His impressive medical career and other enormous talents are described in four sections. Part three deals with his appearance in the courts of law, predominantly as an expert witness, sometimes controversial, often at inquests, often to present his post-mortem findings and once as the defendant.

Keywords: *history, Australian medicine, Patrick Moloney, career.*

Moloney appeared frequently in court as the expert medical witness at inquests and following accidents or violent crime, and once as a plaintiff.

Dr Patrick Moloney, resident surgeon at the Melbourne Hospital, received Ann Galvin complaining of pain between the shoulders, which she said was not due to violence. She died two days after admission. He presented evidence before Dr. Youl at the inquest into her death.

Witnesses confirmed that Mrs Galvin had been hit on the back by her husband, John Galvin when he was drunk. Dr. L. J. Martin deposed that he had first attended the deceased the day of admission and found her suffering from lockjaw and tetanic convulsions. It was before vaccines virtually eliminated the risk of tetanus and before curative antibiotics.

Moloney performed the post mortem examination following her death, finding no evidence of violence to her back but the injury was presumed to have caused tetanus. Others said there was evidence of considerable violence to her back, presumably the autopsy findings are

the more accurate. After the coroner had summed up, the jury brought in a verdict that the deceased died from tetanus as the result of a blow inflicted by her husband, John Galvin. Dr. Youl committed him for trial on a charge of murder.

Evidence was presented at his trial that Ann Galvin suffered a penetrating wound to her foot two weeks earlier and this was a probable source of tetanus, hence the case was dismissed. Galvin committed suicide by shooting himself the following year (The Age, 1867; The Argus, 1867; The Leader, 1868b).

Moloney attended Catherine Smith, aged about twenty years, in her terminal illness and presented details at the inquest before Mr. Candler at the Melbourne Hospital. After eating some raw tomatoes she developed vomiting and abdominal pain. On admission to hospital she was described as blue and collapsed, presumably cyanosed and hypotensive, and failed to respond to medication

The jury returned a verdict that death had been caused by some vegetable matter taken as food,

but that there was not sufficient evidence to identify the vegetable (The Herald, 1868).

Dr Moloney appeared before Mr Candler at the inquest into the death of Mary Glew, aged thirty years in the Melbourne Hospital. She was brought to the operating theatre to be operated on for fistula by Mr Randall who asked her if she desired to be put under the influence of chloroform and she replied in the affirmative. Mr Randall place forty drops of chloroform on a towel and applied it to the mouth and nose of the patient.

Dr Moloney, resident surgeon, entered the theatre soon after, and took the towel from Mr Randall, which he continued to hold to the face of the deceased, adding more chloroform as the woman was in that excited stage which precedes unconsciousness. The deceased soon became unconscious, and, in reply to Mr Randall, Moloney announced that she was fit to commence surgery. Her breathing was at this time laboured, but not such as to cause any alarm. It, however, soon ceased altogether. Restoratives were promptly applied by several medical men to no avail.

A post mortem examination was afterwards made, and Mr Rudall and Dr. Moloney agreed that death was caused by the inhalation of chloroform and was induced by disease of the liver and kidneys, It was stated that the chloroform used was good, and the same as is constantly applied in the Hospital. There was no reason to believe that an undue quantity had been administered. The deceased died in about six minutes from the time when the chloroform was first applied.

The jury found that the deceased died from. the inhalation of chloroform, which was of excellent quality and properly administered, and that no blame should be attached to the medical attendants of the deceased (The Leader, 1868a).

Dr. Maclean presided over a coroner's inquest into the deaths of two Chinese Passengers from the barque Dayspring. The coroner read a medical certificate he had received from Dr. Moloney, the resident physician at the Melbourne Hospital, stating that Mr W. A. Langdon, one of the passengers, and the most

important witness, was still too ill to be removed from the Hospital, and would he compelled to remain there for at least three weeks longer.

The coroner felt there were adequate witnesses to proceed. The court found the Captain, Middleton was guilty of manslaughter of the passengers for providing an inadequate diet when the ship was becalmed in the South China Sea for four weeks, and that the two Chinese men died of scurvy.

It was over a hundred years since Captain James Lind RN, proved that scurvy could be prevented with citrus fruit, and seventy years since daily lemon juice became obligatory for the sailors of the Royal Navy. Middleton was committed for trial (The Age, 1868).

Ten weeks after the onset of a septic illness Moloney was well enough to appear in court again as an expert witness. It emphasises the severity and mortality of septicaemia in the pre-antibiotic era, when many doctors died from diseases contracted at work. An inquest was held in the Hospital by Dr Youl on the body of John Smith, aged fifty-eight years who died in that institution. Three weeks previously he fell some ten feet sustaining a head injury. Smith was taken to the hospital and examined by Dr Moloney who found a slight scalp wound but no apparent skull fracture. It was of course before skull x-rays were available.

Twelve days after admission he developed acute inflammation of the brain and died after a further two days with a diagnosis of acute inflammation of the brain from external violence.

Today it is not clear if Smith had an intracranial haemorrhage, meningitis from an undiagnosed fracture or even a ruptured post traumatic arteriovenous fistula. He lived in the bush eating mainly wild animals so may have had dietary deficiencies to confound problems (The Herald, 1869).

Dr. Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the trial of George Osborne charged with committing a violent assault upon two infants, aged three and five months. Moloney found the elder was severely swollen and bruised about the

face and the side of the head as well as s bleeding from the nose and mouth,. The younger child was bleeding from its mouth.

The Bench sentenced the prisoner to six months' imprisonment, and at the end of that time to find sureties of £20 each to keep the peace for a further period of six months (The Argus, 1869a).

Dr. Moloney attended Mr Marsden at the Melbourne Hospital with injuries sustained in a fight with a Mr Jackson. Moloney informed the police that Marsden should be released on bail prior to a court hearing in which he would be accused of assaulting Jackson as Marsden had in fact, detected Jackson in the commission of a crime and tried to prevent the offence (The Age, 1869b).

Moloney performed a post mortem examination on the body of William Hurst finding a fractured skull base. Hurst had been drinking heavily, fell over twice and was found lying insensible in a bar. He died soon after admission to the Melbourne Hospital. An inquest jury accepted Moloney's findings as the cause of death (The Herald, 1869).

Dr Moloney was an expert witness in the trial of Edward Piggott in the Melbourne Criminal Sessions at the Old Courthouse before his Honour Mr. Justice Williams charged with having killed one George Preston. Preston was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital under Dr Moloney and died the following day with a diagnosis of a ruptured cerebral blood vessel.

Pigott and Preston had a disagreement in a pub and Preston was struck on the head but it was not clear from witness accounts who struck the fatal blow, hence the verdict was not guilty (The Argus, 1869b).

Dr. Moloney attended Margaret McCann, an eight year old little girl when she was admitted to the hospital suffering from severe burns, caused by the explosion of a kerosene tin with which she used to light the fire during the temporary absence of her mother. Moloney found her situation to be hopeless, and she died the following day. At the inquest held by Dr. Youl, the jury found that deceased had died from the

effects of burns accidentally received (The Age, 1869a).

Moloney treated Mrs Ferguson who was suffering from a black eye and other bruises following a brawl with Henry Frieling. She had criticised Freiling for being drunk. Her husband Henry Ferguson came to her rescue and struck Freiling's head with a piece of quartering which unfortunately fractured his skull causing death.

Ferguson was convicted of manslaughter in Prahran with a strong recommendation for clemency in view of the provocation (The Argus, 1870b).

Moloney treated Christina Barry, a young girl between sixteen and seventeen years of age for self-administered lead poisoning with a full recovery. She went to a chemist's shop in Smith Street, and purchased a small quantity of sugar of lead, as she said, to colour her dress.

She was brought before the courts charged with attempted suicide, a crime till decriminalise in 1967. This may not have helped her mental state (The Argus, 1870b).

Dr Moloney, as resident surgeon, attended John Lennox, aged sixty-five when he had a fit working on the wharf in Customs and was conveyed to hospital. Moloney diagnosed sanguinous apoplexy from which Lennox died three hours after admission. He presented this evidence to the inquest was held by Dr. Youl in which the jury returned a verdict in accordance with the medical evidence (Weekly Times 19/3/1870a).

Dr. Moloney, resident physician, attended Charles Edwards who had been stabbed in the left side of the chest. Moloney found a wound which had been deflected upwards by a rib preventing a more severe penetrating injury.

The injury was inflicted by John Allen who was committed for trial (The Argus, 1870a).

Dr. Moloney attended William Carter, a plasterer, aged forty-one, following a fatal accident at work. Carter appeared to suffer an epileptic fit at work and fell from the scaffold, He had a swelling on the upper part of the right side of the head, and a slight abrasion on the

right shoulder with two ribs broken. He remained unconscious in a state of epileptiform convulsions and died four days after admission. At the inquest held before Dr. Youl, the city coroner, the jury returned a verdict of accidental death from epilepsy brought on by external violence (Advocate, 1870b; The Telegraph, St Kilda and Prahan and South Yarra Guardian, 1870).

Dr. Moloney was an expert witness in the inquest on the body of John Walshe in the Melbourne Hospital before Dr. Youl, the City Coroner. Moloney stated that the deceased was brought to the hospital in a state of extreme collapse. He had received a bullet wound in the abdomen. On examining his clothes, Moloney found a small circular opening penetrating his waistcoat, trousers, and shirt. The edges of the opening in the cloth were stained black,

singed and discoloured by gunpowder indicating that the weapon must have been fired within a short distance of the victim.. Moloney found a circular wound in the abdomen just below and to the left of the umbilicus. On probing the wound upwards, and to the right he found the bullet just below the eleventh rib on the right flank which he extracted and demonstrated to the court.

Walshe's condition deteriorated and he died the following day. Moloney's post mortem revealed the bullet had passed through the ascending colon. There was some blood in the abdomen and the intestines were inflamed. Today a laparotomy and closure of the intestinal perforation, perhaps with a partial colectomy and temporary colostomy would have been life-saving. In 1870 Walshe had no chance. Walshe left a widow and six children age between four and seventeen.

Mr. Gerard Henry Supple fired the gun in an attempt to assassinate Mr. G S Smith, a member of parliament, apparently as an Irish Nationalist and Walshe received the fatal shot endeavouring to assist Smith (The Argus, 1870c; The Herald, 1870b).

Dr. Moloney appeared as the expert witness at the inquest before Dr Youl, city coroner, into the death of James Holden, a carpenter, aged

sixty-seven years. Holden suffered a minimal trauma femoral fracture twisting his leg when rising from his seat. He was taken home and then to the hospital the following day. Moloney said that the cause of death had been exhaustion from fracture of the thigh-bone, and the jury returned a verdict in accordance with medical evidence. Today the cause of death is unclear, perhaps severe blood loss, perhaps primary malignant bone and bone marrow disease (Weekly Times, 1870b).

Dr. Moloney attended Arthur Garrett with a severe head injury after Elizabeth O'Connor allegedly struck him on the head with a pick handle. When Moloney stated that Garrett was still unable to appear at the city magistrates court, O'Connor was remanded on bail for a further seven days (Advocate, 1870a).

Sarah Jane Roberts Salt, a girl of fourteen years of age was admitted into the Melbourne Hospital under Dr Moloney suffering from severe burns of her whole body when her clothes caught on fire. Moloney, the resident surgeon, stated at the inquest before Dr. Youl, the city coroner, that the deceased was admitted with severely burns. She was very weak and suffering severely from shock. Moloney considered the case was a hopeless one from the first, The following day she became delirious, and died.

The jury returned a verdict of accidental death through burns (The Herald, 1870a).

Dr Moloney attended Eliza Spruhan when she was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital with fatal burns. She had been ironing near a fire when her clothes caught on fire. Moloney as Resident Medical Officer, informed the inquest held before Dr. Youl, that the deceased was taken to the hospital severely burned over the whole of the back, most of the legs and thighs, and a portion of the left arm. She never rallied, and died, about forty-eight hours after admission.

The jury returned a verdict that the deceased was accidentally burnt and died from the effect. (The Herald, 1871a)

Henry Rock was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital under Dr Moloney with multiple stab

wounds to his neck, chest and arms following a brawl with John Williamson at sea. There were seven cuts in his shirt. Rock was sufficiently recovered to be able to attend the initial court hearing though still an inpatient. Williamson was remanded in custody until the next hearing of the criminal court (The Herald, 1871b).

Dr. Moloney was the expert witness at the inquest into the death of Martin Hehir, a twenty seven year old unmarried labourer, held before the city coroner, Dr. Youl. Hehir was returning home after work, slightly under the influence of liquor, when he was struck in the abdomen by a dray shaft. Hehir had not safely disconnected the horse from the dray and the injury occurred when the horse plunged forward.

Moloney found him to be suffering from a rupture of the muscles of the right side of his abdomen and that a large quantity of intestines protruded through the muscles, being only retained by the skin. Peritonitis inevitably developed, Hehir deteriorated and he died next day.

The jury returned a verdict of accidental death due to inflammation of the bowels from external violence, and that the case was hopeless from the first. Today a laparotomy and repair would not challenge a general surgeon (The Argus, 1871f).

Dr. Moloney attended a Chinaman, Ah John, after he had been stabbed in a robbery and was taken to the hospital. Moloney dressed a wound above the left eye. Subsequently Moloney appeared at the trial of John Kenworthy, a young man of about twenty accused of the assault.

Initially Kenworthy claimed that Ah John stabbed him first but Moloney said that lesion had been inflicted within six or seven weeks. The second press report stated that Ah John was struck over the right eye with a knife, inflicting a dangerous wound, which confined him to the hospital for several days.

Kenworthy was found guilty and sentenced to hard labour on the roads of the colony for five years, and to be twice privately whipped with the cat-o'-nine tails, receiving twenty strokes each time (The Argus, 1871a; 1871b).

An inquest was held by the District Coroner at the Hospital, on the body of Mary Moran, wife of a miner residing at Raywood. She had been admitted for surgery for a cancer performed by Dr. MacGillivray, Hospital Surgeon. Two days after surgery a prescribing error led to her taking carbolic acid which was only discovered when she was unconscious and attempted gastric lavage and stimulants were unsuccessful.

Humphrey Buckler, was for a considerable time wardsman in the Melbourne Hospital and brought an excellent character reference from Dr Moloney.

The jury gave a verdict that deceased came suddenly by her death from accidental poisoning by carbolic acid, and expressed deep regret that the dispenser, John Barker, and the wardsman, Humphrey Buckler, were not more careful in obeying the instructions of the resident surgeon (Bendigo Advertiser, 1871a).

Dr. Patrick Moloney, surgeon at the Melbourne Hospital presented evidence at the inquest, before Dr Youl, city coroner, on the body of Thomas White, a forty eight year old engineer.

White died from the effects of injuries caused by the explosion of gas at the valve-chamber of the waterworks,

Moloney stated that when the deceased was admitted to the hospital he was suffering from a severe burns over the legs, arms, head, face, and back. He was quite sensible and stated that he had lit the match which led to the explosion, contrary to his direct instructions, and that no person was to blame but himself. However he was in a state of collapse and though immediately placed under treatment, he never rallied and died.

Engineers subsequently found extensive leakage from the gas main and other witnesses had detected a strong smell of gas. The court believed the fault lay with White for lighting a match and that no one connected with the company was criminally liable. It was considered his wife might have a civil action against the company for the loss of the services of her husband, and the jury, after consultation, returned a verdict of accidental death.

Companies were rarely found to have any responsibility for work place accidents or deaths in this era and compensation for widows and children was at best by small charitable donations from which business was known to extract a collection fee (Stride, 2021; 2024; The Argus, 1871g; The Weekly Times, 1871).

Dr. Youl held an inquest at the Melbourne Hospital, on the body of William Rodwell, a twenty year old drover. Dr. Moloney stated that when Rodwell was admitted to the hospital he was suffering from a deep lacerated wound in the left groin, and an extensive injury to the left hip cap. A large artery was torn across, a good deal of blood had been lost, and though the bleeding was stopped the patient never rallied and died next morning.

The injury occurred when Rodwell, riding at a fast trot after some drinks, collided with a horse drawn cab, with the shaft of the cab causing the fatal injury. The jury found a verdict of accidental death (The Argus, 1871e).

Dr Moloney appeared as expert witness in the case of Bennett v. Melbourne Omnibus Company in the Supreme Court before Mr. Justice Barry. Bennett claimed that he had been kicked by a horse after dismounting from an omnibus. According to his own account, he received such injuries from being trampled on as prevented him from working at his trade, that of a hat cleaner, and earning £4 a week thereby. Since the occurrence he could earn nothing since he claimed to have become feeble. Bennett sought to recover £300 damages for inflicted injuries.

Dr. Moloney was called on his behalf, but the evidence given by this witness went rather against the plaintiff than in his favour as Moloney testified to the extreme improbability of the plaintiff's suffering such injuries as he had described. On the day after the accident Moloney found Bennett had a sprained wrist, and he put a splint on merely for the sake of precaution. Moloney told Bennett to come again the following week, but Bennett did not come for two weeks. Dr. Moloney remembered Bennett was coming about the hospital for the last two or three years. The jury returned a

verdict for the defendants (The Age, 1871; The Argus, 1871e).

Annetta Levy was admitted under the care of Dr Moloney with fractures of her mandible and clavicle sustained in an accident in the city. John Hemmings was charged with careless driving, however evidence suggested this was an accident in a remarkably busy street. Dr. Moloney deposed that the child was out of danger.

The Bench said that there appeared to have been no carelessness in driving on the part of Hemmings, and discharged him, but intimated that he ought to pay some damage to the father of the child, to reimburse any expenses caused by the accident (The Argus, 1871c).

Joseph Smith, a forty one year old cook, as taken to the Melbourne Hospital but Dr Moloney found him deceased on arrival. He had a sudden onset severe haemorrhage from a large sloughing ulcer on his right thigh in which a vein had burst. At the inquest before Dr Youl, the jury's verdict was death from loss of blood, caused by the accidental rupture of a vein in an ulcerated leg.

One wonders what was the cause of a deep ulcer eroding into a blood vessel and speculates on the possibility of syphilis or a huge varix (The Argus, 1871d).

Caroline Hall, a forty seven year old married but separated lady of intemperate habits was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital under Dr Moloney following an attempted suicide. She had attempted to cut her throat and was in a very weakly state.

Dr. Moloney stated that she progressed well for nearly a fortnight but was then attacked three times with secondary (implying an infected wound) haemorrhage. She required to be fed with a tube which greatly distressed her, she deteriorated and died two weeks after admission.

Moloney presented the clinical information at the inquest held before Dr Youl. The jury found the cause of death was the wound in the throat self-inflicted while of unsound mind, from constant intoxication (The Herald, 1871c; The Argus, 1871h).

Dr Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the Civil Sitting at the Old Court House before his Honour Mr. Justice Williams and a special jury of four in the case of Turner versus. van Hemert. Mrs Turner had an intracapsular fracture of the neck of femur which was not diagnosed immediately by Dr van Hemert. The unusually small jury retired, and after deliberating over an hour returned a verdict for the plaintiff with damages of £230.

The Victorian medical profession collectively were appalled by this decision. Fractured femora can be notoriously difficult to diagnose especially when initially incomplete as was suggested in this case. The physical signs on examination were conflicting and lateral rotation of the leg was absent. Even today with Xray's the diagnosis can remain uncertain until a CT or MRI scan is performed. It was considered that Hemert's reputation and finances had been unfairly damaged by an inaccurate summing up and a minimal size jury (The Argus, 1871i).

Moloney attended Harriot Rees, a little seven year old girl, and subsequently presented his findings at the trial of Ellen Rees, her mother accused of assaulting Harriet. Moloney stated that found Harriet in a very neglected condition. She had several bruises on the upper part of her right side, and the cartilage of one of her ribs had been injured. A witness stated he saw the woman beating the child's head against the walls of her house.

Ellen Rees, a woman of dissipated appearance, pleaded "Guilty" to assaulting her child Harriot. She stated, in extenuation, that she committed the assault when under the influence of drink. The Bench sentenced the woman to three months' hard labour under a section specially provided to meet assaults upon young children.

John Rees, her husband, was summoned for leaving his four children, under 12 years of age, without the means of support. Rees claimed he provided money but Ellen spent in on alcohol, hence the neighbours provided food and clothing for the children. The Bench postponed the further hearing for a week to give the defendant an opportunity of providing suitably for his children (The Argus, 1872).

Dr. Moloney attended Samuel James Saul Williams, a thirty five year old married carpenter and presented his evidence at a subsequent inquest before Dr. Youl. A brick fell on William's head causing a skull fracture. He was an inpatient for thirteen days and discharged himself. He was readmitted nine days later exhibiting symptoms of inflammation of the brain. An operation of trephining was performed by Mr. Rudall and pieces of the bone removed. An abscess was found between the skull and the membranes of the brain. He improved for a few days but deteriorated and died eleven days after readmission.

A verdict was returned that he died from fracture of the skull from external violence. Bacterial infection of the brain, meningitis or a cerebral abscess was usually fatal in the pre-antibiotic era (The Age, 1872a).

Dr. Moloney attended Pat Molloy who was assaulted in a brawl with Sergeant Summerhayes.

Molloy had several contusions on the head and two lacerations. His hand was swollen and the first finger broken. He remained in the hospital for six days and was afterwards treated for some time as an out-patient.

Moloney presented this evidence at a district court before Mr. Call in which Michael Kinane, a blacksmith's assistant, summoned Sergeant Summerhayes for an unlawful assault.

Apparently Mrs Summerhayes was a prostitute before and then after her marriage to Sergeant Summerhayes. Kinane and Molloy were frequent visitors to her house for sexual intercourse and Summerhayes returned home one night to find the pair with his wife provoking the conflict.

Summerhayes denied the allegations. The case was dismissed with £3 3s costs imposed on the defendant (The Age, 1872b).

Dr. Moloney attended Mary Jane Carlton and subsequently presented his findings at the trial of the Rev. Thomas Abraham, and Jane Abraham, his wife, for alleged cruelty to a child at the Emerald Hill Police Court. Moloney found extensive widespread bruises probably inflicted with a heavy stick and facial scalds inflicted with

some extremely hot instrument. She was also suffering from bronchitis and otitis.

After witness statements and an obfuscating defence, the defendants were then committed for trial, bail in the amount of £100 for each being accepted. Subsequently the defendants were found not guilty by a jury to the displeasure of the attending gallery (The Herald, 1872a; The Ballarat Courier, 1872; The Weekly Times, 1872a; Advocate, 1872).

Dr Moloney witnessed the execution of Edward Feeny on the scaffold outside Melbourne Jail and provide the death certificate once Feeny had died when the fall from the scaffold failed to break his neck and Feeny struggled for three minutes before death (The Herald, 1872b).

Mary Francis was conveyed to Dr Moloney with a cut in her arm which required suturing. She had been involved in a domestic brawl with Edward Whitehouse and John Ryan in which she ran her fist and arm through a window laying it open. Whitehouse discharged his revolver many times without inflicting any injury and the police were required to restore law and order.

When the whole unsavoury scenario came to court, Whitehouse who was drunk at the time was ordered to find one surety of £50 to keep the peace for six months. (The Herald, 1872c).

Dr Moloney presented evidence at the inquest into the death of Henry Pyke before the coroner, Mr Candler. Pyke was found on a beach with his throat cut. Dr Moloney, had seen the deceased and had treated him for delirium tremens, noting that his memory was sometimes very much affected, and that his mind could be easily unsettled. A second medical opinion also suggested that Pyke was of unsound mind.

The jury, in a verdict which is seldom found in the colony of Victoria, found that deceased had killed himself while of sound mind. The Mount Alexandra Mail considered the inquest was a debacle in which the jury and doctors displayed a lack of intelligence and understanding. The paper considered 'Coronal inquiries are a great humbug at the best of times, though they are a little better conducted now that medical men no

longer act as coroners' (Mount Alexandra Mail, 1872; Hamilton Spectator, 1872).

Moloney treated David Randall McCabe with a broken leg apparently uneventfully until McCabe took Moloney to court charged with stealing his money. The case was dismissed (The Herald, 1873).

Dr. Moloney presented his post mortem finding at the inquest into the sudden death of William Smith before Dr Youl. Smith was a known heavy drinker with bouts of delirium tremens. Moloney considered death was due to alcoholic poisoning and the jury concurred (The Argus, 1873b).

Dr McRea presented the evidence of Dr Moloney's post mortem examination of the body of Gustav Haasey, a forty one year old cook, to the inquest under Dr Youl. A convicted paedophile, Haasey was drunk in gaol and placed in the gaol hospital where he died. Moloney considered delirium tremens was the cause of death and the jury concurred (The Argus, 1873a).

The trial of George Gumperston, licensee of the All Nations Hotel, charged with allowing disorderly women on his premises was delayed as the barmaid, a primary witness, was unwell and proffered a sick certificate provided by D Moloney. It was said that her indisposition followed a thrashing by the accused (The Herald, 1874c).

Dr Moloney was summoned to the Post-Office Club Hotel to attend Mr H. L. Sharpe who was suffering from recurrent prolonged fits. About three years previously Mr. Sharpe sustained an injury to the skull falling down a flight of stairs at the Union Club with resultant fits since. When Moloney arrived Sharpe was found lying on the floor quite dead, with his head against the door. An inquest on the remains was proposed (The Argus, 1875c).

Dr Moloney was summoned to see Elizabeth Gardner in her home but found she was deceased on arrival. He subsequently performed an autopsy and presented his findings at the inquest under Dr Youl. Moloney stated that the cause of death was alcoholic poisoning. According to a witness she was scarcely ever

sober. The jury found a verdict to that effect (The Herald, 1874a; 1874b).

Dr Moloney attended Robert Burns aged eighteen months, the son of Edward Henry Burns, at the Industry Schools and considered he would not live long, though no clinical details are given. Mr. Candler held an inquest on the body of the boy. Robert's mother died three weeks ago and the boy died in the arms of his wet nurse.

Dr. Ram performed the post mortem examination and found the cause of death to be effusion of serum into the brain, perhaps hydrocephalus. A verdict was returned in accordance with the medical evidence (The Age, 1874a).

Mary Curry was charged with insulting behaviour while en route to see Dr Moloney at his practice now in Lonsdale Street (The Age, 1874b).

Dr Moloney attended Ah Ching, a Mongolian waiter, following a fight in which Ching sustained a scalp wound and slight concussion. The trial of his assailant was delayed as Moloney issued a certificate requesting more time for recovery.

John Strangeways was accused of assaulting Ah Ching in a Chinese cook shop. Strangeways, intoxicated at the time, wanted some roast duck but could not pay for this hence a fight broke out. Mr. Sturt, P.M., decreed a fine of 20s., with £5 costs to go to Ah Ching, less £1 to the doctor would meet the case in default of a month's imprisonment (The Argus 11/11/1874a; 1874b).

Dr. Moloney attended John Flannagan in the Melbourne Gaol Hospital diagnosing delirium tremens and epilepsy. Flanagan, charged with threatening to kill his wife, subsequently died and at the inquest before Dr Youl, Dr McCrae presented his post mortem findings concurring with Moloney's diagnosis of delirium tremens and the jury agreed with the medical verdict (The Weekly Times, 1785).

The will of James Haren, deceased, leaving his assets to his wife, was challenged in court before his Honour Mr. Justice Molesworth by Harris's

brother on the grounds of persuasion when mentally incompetent. Dr Moloney had previously attended James Haren failing to find any evidence of mental disfunction and the case was dismissed (The Argus, 1875d).

An inquest before Dr Youl investigated the death of Robert Berth in the Melbourne Hospital. Dr Beaney, an experienced surgeon, performed a lithotomy with a peritoneal incision for an unusually large bladder stone. Dr Moloney was one of those present in theatre. While Beaney had performed similar operations in some three minutes, the size of the stone, weighing six ounces and measuring six inches by five inches, complicated the operation which took an hour and thirty minutes. Moloney and others suggested crushing the stone but no equipment was available for this. A considerable degree of force was required to remove the stone.

Berth died four days post-operatively, though he did receive brandy and champagne as he deteriorated. Beaney's professional competence was questioned. At post mortem a two inch tear was found in the rectum with a collection of faeculent fluid in the pelvis.

Clearly the rectal laceration was an unfortunate adverse outcome of a difficult operation and death from peritonitis was inevitable without a post operative laparotomy as one hopes would happen today to repair the lesion.

Legal opinion suggested that Beaney should be charged with manslaughter. The jury took the viewpoint that the laceration was a most unfortunate event in a difficult operation occurring to a most competent surgeon and it would be inappropriate to blight his career with a verdict of negligence. They did however point out that the hospital rule of difficult cases being discussed by four hospital surgeons had not been observed and must be in future (Ballarat Courier, 1875; The Age, 1875; The Argu, 1875b; Weekly Times, 1876).

Dr Moloney and others on a subcommittee of the Melbourne Hospital Committee reviewed the death of a boy, Michael Barry, who died at the end of an operation by Dr Beaney. There were allegations in the press that the anaesthetist,

Dr Lewellin, gave chloroform without due care and attention to the boy, and ordered water and brandy causing choking.

Medical evidence indicated that the chloroform was given with normal anaesthetic skill and that Beaney ordered the oral fluids. Barry appears to have died of respiratory failure from chloroform perhaps exacerbated by inhalation of fluids, but no blame was attached to Lewellin who appeared to follow normal procedures. The article in the press was totally refuted (The Argus, 1875a).

Dr Moloney attended Thomas Gustavus Donahoo, a twenty six year old clerk, before his death. Moloney's death certificate was presented at an inquest held at East Melbourne, by Dr Youl, the city coroner stating that he died a natural death from syncope, due to an aneurysm. however the postmortem revealed that death resulted from congestion of the lungs, with effusion into the bronchial chambers. There was no aneurysm!

Subsequently Moloney stated that he thought anaemia was the cause of death, not an aneurysm! The jury returned a verdict in accordance with the autopsy result (The Herald, 1876; The Age, 1876).

Moloney appeared again in court as an expert witness. Mr. Richard Cogan, a miner, sued Mr. J. S. Hosie, the proprietor of the Turkish baths, for damages for injuries he had received through the alleged negligence of the defendant's servant, in the Supreme Court yesterday, before the Chief Justice and a jury of six.

In the course of the operations the attendant was about to "hose" Cogan with cold water, instead, however, of Cogan receiving cold water, a quantity of hot water was poured upon his head, which severely scalded his head and neck, and in consequence he was treated by Dr. Moloney for a month. The effect of the accident was that his hair was changed from a dark brown to a grey colour, and Dr. Moloney stated that the injuries were likely to be of a permanent nature

The defendant paid £100 into Court as sufficient compensation, but Cogan alleged that this was not sufficient, as owing to the accident he had

been unable to prosecute his intended trip to Queensland, and his expenses while on the sick leave were over £90.

Dr, Moloney at one time undertook to settle the matter, as he said very foolishly and unsuccessfully. Moloney finally came to the conclusion that he was not made to be an arbitrator and gave up the attempt as a bad job. The jury found in favour of the defendant concluding the damages paid were adequate (The Australasian, 1877; The Argus, 1877a).

Mr J, H. Dunne, a phenomenally successful criminal barrister, judge and newspaper proprietor died suddenly aged sixty seven. Moloney was in the house when Dunne was taken ill but Dunne declined a medical opinion.

Dr Youl, city coroner, held an inquest, on the body. Edmund Hunt, M.D., duly qualified medical practitioner, stated that he had performed a post-mortem examination of the body finding advanced cirrhosis and severe cardiac fatty degeneration as the major abnormalities. Witnesses gave a history of heavy drinking. The jury returned a verdict of death from alcoholic poisoning (The Herald, 1877).

Dr Moloney was an expert witness at the trial of John Hunter, aged about thirty, on a charge of murdering Leicester Dean, before Mr. Justice Molesworth at the Central Criminal Court. Evidence indicated that Dean initiated the fight and initially survived the stab wounds dying thirteen days later. Moloney was requested by the defence for the purpose of showing the death was actually due to the gout from which the deceased had been suffering, and his evidence was to the effect that the excitement of a struggle would in a gouty subject, probably cause the disease to fly to the brain!

There were seventeen stab wounds on the man's body, all superficial, the deceased had been subject to gout, and the cause of death was attributed to delirium and inflammation of the membranes of the brain, caused by the wounds and mental excitement!

The judge having summed up, the jury retired, and in twenty minutes, apparently unimpressed by the bizarre medical opinions, returned a

verdict of guilty of manslaughter, with a recommendation for mercy on account of the provocation the prisoner had received. His Honor sentenced Hunter to four months' imprisonment with hard labour (The Age, 1877).

A seaman named William Millar, of The Firefly, produced a medical certificate from Dr Moloney, to explain his absence from duty without leave when charged in court. However as he refused to be examined by a doctor the captain had procured, he was found guilty and the magistrates sent him to gaol for six weeks, with hard labour (The Age 10/8/1878).

Dr Moloney attended Joseph Oxe, a thirty two year old general servant, in his terminal illness. When he lapsed into unconsciousness he was admitted to hospital and died. Dr Scott deposed at the inquest under Mr Candler that the cause of death was disease of the kidneys, and the jury found a verdict to that effect, though no supportive evidence was presented (The Herald, 1878a).

Dr Moloney attended a girl named Ellen O'Connor following an assault. A glass was thrown at her and she sustained a skull fracture and profuse blood loss. Moloney considered the blow was of great violence such that he was required to remove fragments of glass from her skull. Initially Ellen appeared well but symptoms of brain infection set in, presumably meningitis, and she was re-admitted to the hospital, The next day, according to the testimony of Dr Murray at the trial of the perpetrator, Smith Brown, the girl became delirious and her life for a time was despaired of. Now her condition remained exceedingly critical, possibly requiring major and hazardous surgery.

The bench remanded the case pending the medical outcome (The Herald, 1878b).

Moloney examined a lady named Anna Fulton who claimed to have been 'outraged' by a cabman Tommy Baker. He had attempted rape, though the Age prefers to print the documented euphemisms, however she was rescued by a passer-by. Moloney established that she was 'virtuous' but covered in bruises and wounds. The following day, Fulton was stated to be slightly better, although the shock to her system

is so great that she has been unable to eat any solid food since the assault.

Baker's fellow cabbies circulated a statement to the effect that the woman was a ribald character and had been guilty of 'loose behaviour' with several of them, while several of the leading citizens of Melbourne in whose employment Anne Fulton has been, provided testimonials all declaring her to be sober, honest and industrious. Baker was arrested and remanded in custody at the Emerald Hill Court (The Age, 1879a).

Dr. Moloney was called upon to see Peter McGregor, a fifty eight year old retired squatter, who collapsed suddenly at his residence in the Fechan's City Arms Hotel. However, McGregor expired before Moloney's arrival, presumably of natural causes.

Dr. Youl held an inquest upon McGregor's body. Bridget Feehan, wife of the landlord of the City Arms Hotel, deposed that deceased had stopped for three months and generally enjoyed good health. He did not drink to excess. He became unwell with a head ache followed by a shivering fit. He was seen by a chemist and initially refused his advice to see a doctor.

Moloney subsequently made a post mortem examination of the deceased's body and found nearly all the internal organs diseased. The cause of death was apoplexy from disease of the brain. The jury returned a verdict to that effect (The Age, 1879b; 1879c).

Dr Moloney was summoned to attend Charles Quinot, an eighty year old Frenchman, but he died suddenly before the doctor arrived. Moloney performed the autopsy and revealed at the inquest before Dr Youl that Quinot died with a ruptured heart, a verdict duly returned by the jury (The Argus, 1879a; 1879c).

Moloney was summoned to see Mr John Bergin but he died before Moloney arrived. He had been unwell for a few days with an ulcerated tongue and throat before deteriorating suddenly. An inquest was expected (The Argus, 1879b).

Dr Moloney performed a post mortem examination upon the naked body of a male infant approximately six days old found by the

side of the railway line and presented the results that the baby was still born to an inquest held by Dr Youl. The jury found that deceased was wilfully left by some person or persons unknown. The infant can hardly be six days old and stillborn (The Argus, 1880; The Record and Emerald Hill and Sandwich Advertiser, 1880)!

Dr Moloney deposed at a coronial inquest that Pierce Cosson, a forty year old farmer who had been ailing and was found dead in bed, died of pulmonary consumption, though no clinical or post mortem information is given. The jury found a verdict to that effect (The Herald, 1880).

Dr. Moloney attended a woman named Elizabeth Meadows, aged thirty seven years, of Leichhardt-street, and advised that she should be removed to the hospital. She was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital in an insensible condition. She never rallied and died. An inquest would be held (The Argus, 1881a).

The city coroner, Dr. Youl, held an inquest in Melbourne on the body of Margaret Pollovineo, who died shortly after her fifth confinement, leaving three living children. James Pollovineo, a grocer, residing in Little Collins Street, said that deceased was his twenty eight year old wife. When the child was born at 3.00am, her condition deteriorated due to a postpartum haemorrhage. Dr Moloney declined to attend when requested as he had not been engaged for her pregnancy and by the time another doctor, Dr. Charles S. Ryan, arrived, she had died. Her midwife had been delivering babies for twenty years but was unqualified and unlicensed.

Dr Ryan performed the postmortem examination and the jury returned a verdict that the cause of death was haemorrhage in accordance with the medical testimony.

Dr. Moloney was summoned to attend an unknown man about sixty years of age, who was eating his dinner, when it was seen that he was choking, but before the doctor arrived the man was deceased. A piece of meat was afterwards extracted from the man's throat. The body was removed to the morgue to await identification and an inquest.. The deceased had had his left leg amputated above the knee and was dressed in dark coat and trousers and

brown vest. He had some cash in his pocket and a return railway ticket from Richmond.

He was identified as Samuel Taylor, a fifty seven year old dairyman. At his inquest before Dr Youl, Dr Moloney stated that the retrieved piece of meat was eight inches long and the jury agreed that the deceased was accidentally choked by a piece of meat (The Argus, 1881b).

Anthony Burke was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital with a non-fatal head injury inflicted with a stone by his daughter and subsequently died in hospital of nosocomial erysipelas. Dr Youl at the inquest was extremely critical of the hospital declaring that the Melbourne Hospital ought to be pulled down altogether, for it was saturated with erysipelas and pyaemia.

Dr Moloney was involved in the subsequent meeting of the sanitary committee to address these accusations. The majority of the doctors believed these accusations had significant validity and that a report with recommendations be sent to the Hospital Committee.

Moloney thought the statement of Dr. Youl was not to be taken too literally, as it might just as well be said that Melbourne was saturated with erysipelas. He had erysipelas cases lately, the germs were always about, and it only wanted the condition of the patient's health or some local injury to create it He would not perform operations in some cases on account of the risk he would run. Moloney believed that the old building should be pulled down and a couple of pavilions built.

Dr. Moloney said the class of persons who brought the disease in were the same as the man Burke. The place he lived in was a narrow, right-of-way, all the women in the place drank. The house he lived in appeared as if were never scrubbed, and he would have had erysipelas at home as well as in the hospital. Dr. Moloney advocated a proper ward for these cases and thought that with a little alteration the pavilion might be made perfect, the central part of the building pulled down and new pavilions erected with but little encroachment on the garden, and only acute cases admitted.

The Argus published a sarcastic editorial praising Dr. Youl for providing a service to the community by calling public attention to the disgraceful state of the Melbourne Hospital. The editor thought Youl was doubtless aware that he would incur the undying hatred of the professional committee, who bitterly resent interference with their "Divine right" to mismanage the institution in any way they please. Under the circumstances, Youl will not feel surprised at the prompt exhibition of their malignity by removing him from the role of coroner.

The Editor was much in favour of an independent committee acting to improve the hospital.

At the ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital held yesterday afternoon, Professor Elkington brought up the report of the committee proposing major reconstruction rather than relocation or demolition (The Herald, 1882a; The Age, 1882; The Argus, 1882f; The Argus, 1882g).

Dr Moloney appeared as an expert witness for James Billett Snook in his action against the Board of Land and Works following the Jolimont railway accident. Moloney found that the plaintiff was suffering from an aggravated spinal shock such that his health continued to rapidly deteriorate so that from being a young active man, he became a broken-down invalid and would in all human probability continue so. Snook was awarded damages of £1500 (Mount Alexander Mail, 1882b).

Dr Moloney attended Ellen Maher and removed a bullet from her groin after she had been shot by Arthur Sieber a Hungarian man in a hotel. In an ensuing fracas Sieber was overwhelmed by a policeman and another lodger. He endeavoured unsuccessfully to commit suicide by stabbing himself just below the heart.

The prosecution was initially delayed owing to the poor health of a witness and the slow recovery of Sieber whose survival was initially uncertain. He was committed to stand trial for attempted murder in the Central Criminal Court on Monday the 17th July. Sieber was found guilty

and sentenced to death, but his sentence was commuted to 20 years imprisonment by the Executive Council (The Express and Telegraph, 1882; Mount Alexander Mail, 1882a; The Herald, 1882b; The Australasian, 1882; Illustrated Australian News, 1882).

Moloney appeared as an expert witness in another case of litigation following the Jolimont railway accident. The action was brought by Mr. J. H. Cole, accountant, against the Board of Land and Works, in the Supreme Court before his Honour Mr. Justice Holroyd to recover damages for injuries he sustained in the accident. Moloney found incipient consumption on examination of the chest which he thought unrelated to the accident.

Others stated that his general state of health before the accident was excellent and that he was full of life and activity. Since the accident he had become completely broken down, melancholy, and depressed.

Cole claimed £8,500 and the jury after deliberating about an hour and a half, gave a verdict for the plaintiff of £3,250 damages (The Argus, 1882h).

Dr P. Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the City Court before his Worship Mr Call and a bench of justices. Maximilian Dinon, a wine shop keeper was prosecuted for assaulting a police man and the defence claimed he suffered from police brutality during the affray.

Dinon threw the first punch aiming for Constable Burton but striking constable Nixon. Police batons were used to subdue Dinon, perhaps more than necessary according to witnesses. Dinon was taken to hospital and some bleeding facial wounds dressed following which he was discharged. Moloney had examined the defendant finding a broken arm though this had been previously broken. Moloney considered that more than ordinary force had been used. He also considered the wounds dangerous on account of the prevalence of erysipelas. Dr Moloney said that a person might recover from the most dangerous injury and die from the effects of the most slight wound.

Mr Call thought the case for the prosecution was more consistent all through than that put before them for the defence and would impose only a nominal penalty on the defendant, who had evidently suffered a good deal, He therefore fined him one shillings in each case.

The paper understood that an action would be brought subsequently in the County Court for damages against the police (The Herald, 1882c).

Dr Moloney examined Mr Charles Lucas following his injuries sustained in the Jolimont accident and reported severe injuries. Lucas sued the Board of Land and Homes in the Supreme Court Civil Sittings before Mr. Justice Holroyd and a special jury of twelve.

Mr Lucas claimed to have received a blow on his neck and was so injured that he was unable to attend to his business for six weeks because his spine was slightly injured and he suffered from loss of memory and was occasionally at night unable to sleep. He was also be affected by the shock that he did not now travel in the tram but came to Melbourne in a buggy

Other doctors said that they had examined the plaintiff several times On the first occasion there was a slight swelling on the neck, but it afterwards disappeared. They considered he was not permanently injured.

The jury after deliberating two hours returned a verdict for the plaintiff damages of £3,250 in addition to the sums paid into Court (The Argus, 1882e).

Dr Moloney was asked to give a second opinion in the case of Mr W J Woolcott who was injured by the accident which happened to the 2.20 p m train to St Kilda. Dr Moloney was of opinion that Mr Woolcott has sustained a very severe shock, and that it will be some time before he will be able to get about again.

Dr Moloney was cited as an expert witness in the case of Mr W J Woolcott versus the Board of Land and Works to recover damages from the defendant for injuries he sustained in a train crash caused by their negligence He sustained a severe nervous shock, was confined to his home for a fortnight. He was treated by Moloney who considered Woolcott was suffering from the

effects of the shock and Moloney anticipated that it would be some months before he recovered.

Drs Cree and Shields said that they had examined the plaintiff and were of opinion that he was not so seriously hurt as was represented. The jury gave a verdict for the plaintiff for £500 (The Argus, 1882d; 1882i).

Dr Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the case of Mr A Clarke vs the Board Of Land and Works Civil Sittings before Michaelmas term. Moloney stated that Clarke was injured in a train crash suffering concussion, a spinal injury and severe shock. The jury, after deliberating about three quarters of an hour, returned a verdict for the plaintiff with damages £1,500 (The Argus, 1882c).

Dr Moloney presented his clinical findings at an inquest at the Melbourne Hospital, on the body of Mary Haywood, aged thirty nine, before Mr. Candler, Coroner.

The deceased was struck by a cyclist and fell on the road. She was able to recover and return home with grazes of her face, hands, shoulders, and neck which were dressed in the hospital. Her lesions were then treated at home with the application of thirteen leeches.

One hand swelled, and the swelling went up the arm. Her legs had little red pimples on them, and as she was getting worse she saw Moloney and was admitted to the Melbourne Hospital.

Her left hand was swollen and inflamed. The elbow and knee joints became inflamed, and she deteriorated and died.

Post-mortem examination of her body revealed that the cause of death was blood poisoning or septicaemia caused by her injuries. The jury found that the deceased died from blood poisoning, contracted before her admission to the hospital, in certain injuries and abrasions, caused by her having been accidentally knocked down by a bicycle (The Argus, 1883b).

Dr Moloney appeared as expert witness in the case of William Dwyer versus the Body of Land and Works before His Honour Mr. Justice Higinbotham and Special Juries of Twelve in the

Supreme Court Old Court House for damages sustained in a train crash. Dwyer claimed.£1000 damages for injuries which he alleged he had sustained in the collision on the Hawthorne railway line. He was struck on the back of the head with a piece of timber and knocked down. After about half-an hour, he was able to proceed to Richmond and went from that station to Melbourne by train. He attended the hospital and was examined twice,

The doctors who examined the plaintiff on behalf of the Government said that they found nothing wrong with him Dr Moloney stated that he suffered from a severe shock to his system for which the jury's verdict for the plaintiff was for £10 10s damages (The Argus, 1883d; Evelyn Observer and South and East Bourke Record, 1883).

Moloney and the doctors engaged in cases against the Board of Land and Works, came in for some hard raps in Mr Justice Williams's court. In cross examining Dr Moloney, Mr Purves asked 'What is paraplegia ?' 'Loss Of power in the lower extremities' answered Dr Moloney. 'That is right,' said Mr Purves, amid the laughter of the court, and so counsel proceed to question the doctor somewhat arrogantly on his medical knowledge, but the doctor was not proved at fault anywhere (The Herald, 1883f).

Dr Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the case of Mrs. Charlotte Lawler, a publican of Emerald-hill, against the Board of Land and Works before Mr. Justice Williams and a special jury of twelve for the recovery of £3500 damages for injuries sustained in the Hawthorn railway accident.

Moloney found an injury to the lower part of the spine resulting in attacks of sciatica.

She had received blows on the legs which had blackened them below the knee and also bruises on the hip and face. She had suffered from internal haemorrhage and her legs had continued quite cold in spite of the warmest clothing on her bed. She had also been afflicted with hysteria, which, in the opinion of Dr. Moloney, would not disappear under three or four years.

She calculated that she had made a considerable loss in her business, her inability to look after the hotel cost about £5 per week, and she had had to keep her son at home from his usual occupation to manage for her during her illness. The plaintiff, while under cross-examination, became hysterical and was allowed to leave the court.

The testimony of her medical witnesses including Moloney was contradicted by Dr. McCrea and two other doctors who examined her on behalf of the Government. The bruises on the legs, one on the hip, and a slight bruise on the face were admitted, but beyond these and a slight irregularity of the pulse they saw no evidence of disease or injury. They found no paralysis of motion and sensation, and at their examination found all the organs in a natural state; She suffered from hysteria, which she would recover from completely in a few months

The jury returned a verdict assessing the plaintiff's damages at £1001 10s., £350 of this amount being for consolation for injury and loss, the remainder going for expenses, including medical attendance (The Age, 1883b; The Argus, 1883e).

Dr. Moloney and Dr. Johnston gave evidence in the case of George Edward Cuthill, a clerk in the English, Scottish and Australian Chartered Bank against the Board of Land and Works at the Arbitration Board following his injury in a train crash. He was travelling in the Box-hill train, and did not feel, the shock much at the time of the collision, being able to assist others who were more injured than himself. He walked home, and the next day felt a great stiffness all over the body. Subsequently he became worse and was unable to perform his duties at the bank for some time.

Moloney diagnosed a broken knee joint, and several internal injuries, and that his eyesight was impaired to such an extent that he would never again be able to work at his trade, or if he did he would be unable to earn what he had been in the habit of receiving, fourteen shillings a day. The Government doctors expected a full recovery in two months.

Tho. claimant asked for £2500 and the board subsequently awarded Cuthill £420 (Leader, 1883a; Geelong Advertiser, 1883).

Moloney and three other doctors attended Mr Beck following his injury in train crash. He claimed £5000 for injuries he sustained in the Hawthorn railway accident and was awarded £1737 (Hamilton Spectator, 1883; Kerang Times and Swan Hill Gazette, 1883).

Dr Moloney gave evidence in the case of Andrew Anderson and William Henry Anderson, the thirteen year old son of Andrew Anderson of Brighton v the Board of Land and Works who were injured in a train crash.

William Anderson was knocked unconscious in the crash. He had a lacerated wound about 3in broad, extending from the top of the forehead to the back of the ear. The loss of blood

from the wound was very great owing to several small arteries being divided. The right forearm was fractured, and there were several wounds on the same arm just above the elbow which interfered very much with the adjustment of the splints.

Subsequently he frequently complained of being tired and was troubled with flashes of light before the eyes Under the most favourable circumstances it would be twelve months before the boy would continue his scholastic studies.

Andrew Anderson was also unconscious and required assistance to be removed from the wreckage. his legs badly bruised about the muscles of the calf. For some time after the accident he was suffering from nervousness which might he generally attributed to the shock of the collision.

The case was adjourned with the verdict to be delivered later (The Argus, 1883c).

Moloney appeared as expert witness in the case of Currie v the Borough of Flemington and Kensington before his Honor Mr Justice Williams. Currie was walking home when he fell into a hole in a road and broke his ankle joint. Tho plaintiff was ill for seven weeks, and Dr Moloney stated that at his ago the injury which he had received would render his ankle-joint

permanently stiff. Currie sued for £5000 damages and the jury found a verdict for the plaintiff for £1050 (The Herald, 1883e; Leader, 1883b).

Dr Moloney was called to see Edward Greenfield, aged twenty two who had shot himself when his advances were rejected by a lady. Moloney found a young man lying dead in the sitting room in a pool of blood.

At the subsequent inquest, the jury found that the deceased shot himself, adding that there was no evidence to show the state of his mind at the time (The Herald, 1883c; Illustrated Australian News, 1883).

Dr Moloney was requested to see Frances Steel, a woman acting as servant in Gertrude Street where he was attending a Mrs. Sullivan. He found Mrs Steel had just given birth and on his requested search, the body of an infant female child was found in one of the pans of the outhouse in the rear of the dwelling. The doctor concluded that it was a case of child murder and advised communication with the police.

At the subsequent inquest before Dr Youl, Moloney presented his post mortem finding that the infant died at birth without taking one breath. The jury returned a verdict of death from suffocation at birth and Steel was charged with murder. Steel was subsequently charged at the Central Criminal Court with concealing a birth and infant death, but no reporting of the outcome appears in the press (The Age, 1883a; 1883c; The Herald, 1883a; 1883b; 1883d; The Argus, 1883a).

Dr Moloney was summoned to see Mr Thomas Jackson who collapsed suddenly at the Victoria Coffee Palace. A traveller for Mr John Morris, Iron Merchant, Jackson had planned to take the first train to Ballarat, however life was extinct when Dr Moloney arrived. Moloney subsequently made a post-mortem examination of the body, and found that Dr. Youl held an inquest at the Melbourne Morgue into the body of Jackson and the jury duly returned a verdict of death from an aortic aneurysm (The Herald, 1883a; The Argus, 1883a).

Dr Moloney and several other doctors examined Mr Teague after he was injured in the Clunes railway collision and their opinions were presented in court when Teague sued for damages. He claimed to be an elderly man incapacitated by the railway accident from following his business of a mining engineer which had also turned his hair white.

The judge reprimanded the doctors as their opinions differed from paralysis to palsy to fanciful morbid imagination to nervous shock, leaving the jury bewildered. He considered they should have met previously to achieve a common diagnosis, a difficult requirement in the absence of brain scans and limited understanding of physical signs and ambiguous symptoms.

The jury however, found for the plaintiff for £1250 in addition to the £500 paid into court (Mount Alexander Mail, 1883c).

Dr Moloney presented evidence at the inquest on inquest on the body of Michael Connelly before the coroner, Dr Youl. The deceased, a carpenter by trade and age about forty, had a nail penetrate his foot which was removed. He did not take much notice of the injury until lockjaw set in, and on the advice of Dr Moloney, was removed to the Melbourne Hospital, where he died the following day.

The jury found that the deceased died from tetanus caused by accidentally running a nail into his foot (The Argus, 1884c).

Dr Moloney attended Patrick M'Cormick following an affray with Constable Robert Callender. McCormick according to his wife was sick in bed and vomiting up blood, though details of any injury are lacking. He was unable to attend court.

Callender appeared at the Fitzroy Court before the Mayor, Mr Brooks, on summons charged with having unlawfully assaulted M'Cormick. Brooks decided would be unfair to the defendant to keep the charge hanging over his head. After a lengthy negotiation with the other magistrate, the Mayor struck the case out though a fresh summons may be issued subsequently (The Herald, 1884b).

The hearing of the action of Mr Alfred Bradshaw against the Victorian Railway Commissioners for the recovery of £1500 as compensation for the injuries received in the Little River railway accident was heard before Mr Justice Williams and a jury of twelve.

Dr Moloney appeared on behalf of Bradshaw as one of the expert medical witnesses. Moloney considered Bradshaw was suffering from the loss of assimilative power, due originally to nervous shock. He would require rest, and to be treated in some hydropathic institution in order to recover. His charges were £20.

The case was initially adjourned, but subsequently Bradshaw, was awarded £575 in addition to £659 paid into court by the railway commissioners (The Herald, 1884a; Geelong Advertiser, 1884).

A medical practitioner, Mr. J. Tuthill, was sued in the Supreme Court before Mr. Justice Williams and a special jury of twelve. by William Casement, of Euroa, for £300 damages for mistreatment of a fractured wrist. Casement was riding a bicycle and met with an accident by which his wrist was dislocated and one of the bones was fractured. Tuthill reduced the dislocation and bandaged the wrist. The plaintiff alleged that this operation had been performed so unskillfully that the fractured bone had not properly healed, and that there was a deformity at the side of the wrist.

The fracture was an "impacted" one, and Dr. Caffyn, who was called for the plaintiff, stated that, in his opinion, the defendant should have endeavoured to replace the broken bone in its proper position. The defendant stated that Casement was brought home in a state of complete collapse, and he had to give him stimulants before attempting any operation. After examination he discovered that the wrist was dislocated, and that there was an impacted fracture. The bones were, however, so closely impacted that he could not separate them, and therefore had to be content with reducing the dislocation and bandaging the wrist. Drs Moloney and Dr. O'Hara, who were called for the defence, stated that defendant had adopted the proper treatment in such cases and the jury

gave a verdict for the defendant (The Argus, 1884a; Argus, 1884b; Europa Advertiser, 1884).

Dr. Ford and Dr. Moloney appeared in the City Court to confirm that Grace Darcy, a married woman of respectable appearance was suffering from insanity (The Age, 1885a).

Dr Moloney appeared as an expert witness in the case of Kelly v. the Victorian Railway Commissioners, before Judge Williams, in which the plaintiff claimed £760 damages for injuries sustained in crossing the railway line by a public footway. A truck had been allowed to remain on and obstruct a public crossing and one of its buffers struck Kelly.

Dr Moloney was of opinion that he was seriously injured, two lumps on the ribs having been caused by the injury and he was hospitalised for several weeks. The plaintiff had fallen away generally since the accident and lost two stone in weight. The case was adjourned for a week and subsequently the jury awarded £350 damages (The Herald, 1885; Bendigo Advertiser, 1885).

Mr. N. J. Williams, a commission agent, sued Mr. E. Klingender, solicitor, for damages for assault in the Supreme Court before Mr. Justice Cope and jury of six. The plaintiff complained the defendant seized him by the neck with both hands and throttled him till he was insensible, and then threw him violently on the floor.

Dr. Moloney said he knew that Mr. Williams had been in bad health with purpura for some years past and that the slightest pressure on his skin would produce a bruise. Klingender denied the charge but the jury found in favour of Williams awarding £500 in damages Moloney (The Age, 1885b; Weekly Times, 1885).

Dr. Moloney and others attended Rose Jessie Gordon Herbert, a tailoress living at Brighton, who was a passenger on the express train to Brighton when it crashed. She sustained a dislocation of the shoulder joint, a head wound and a fractured lumbar spine.

These doctors gave it as their opinion that the injuries to the spine were profoundly serious, that it was doubtful if she would ever fully recover from them, and that in any case the

process of recover would be long and tedious one.

Rose Herbert sued the Railway Commissioners in the Supreme Court yesterday, before his Honour Mr. Justice Williams and a special jury of 12 for £5000 damages. The jury returned a verdict for £3500 (The Argus, 1887; Ovens and Murray Advertiser, 1887).

An application was made in the Supreme Court before Mr Justice A'Beckett, on behalf of Messrs. Robert Brough and Dion George Boucicault for an injunction to restrain Mr John Alfred Wilson, the owner of the adjoining Palace Hotel, from allowing noxious vapours and offensive smell from the defendant's kitchen at the Palace Hotel,

Dr P Moloney and others testified to the effect that the complaints made against the defendant were greatly exaggerated and that the inconvenience caused by the smells, heat, etc. was such that no reasonable man would complain of.

The Justice declared that the defendant should give notice of the kitchen being in use and if there was still a dispute, the matter should be tried before a jury (The Argus, 1889b).

Mary Ann O'Hagan, licensee of the Nicholson Hotel, corner of Nicholson and Palmerston Streets, Carlton, was proceeded against at the local police court yesterday for two breaches of the licensing Act, Sunday trading and having the door leading to the bar open during prohibited hours. As a result of the hotel being open there was a dispute between John Hayes and Constable Gorin in the execution of his duty for which Hayes was charged.

Hayes produced a certificate signed by Dr. Moloney certifying that at the time referred to he was suffering from the effects of a dislocated collar bone. Gorin said he did not lay a hand on him or strike Hayes. The bench considered the charge proved and inflicted a fine of thirty shillings in default of the days imprisonment (The Age 2/4/1889a).

Dr. P. Moloney was prosecuted at the District Court by the Central Board of Health for neglecting to notify the board of the outbreak of

a case of typhoid fever, as was required by the Amended Health Act. Moloney apologised for the omission, though he had reported typhoid on the death certificate. When he agreed pay ten guineas costs, the prosecution was withdrawn.

'Fiat Justitia' wrote to the Age complaining about the lack of justice writing, 'The withdrawal of the charge against Dr. Patrick Moloney, who recently neglected to report a case of typhoid fever, is a discouraging example of the administration of justice in Melbourne. The excuse that he had given a true certificate of death was a very poor one. There is at present no law compelling doctors not to certify falsely, but they are required to report the occurrence of certain diseases. The fact of a medical man being wealthy, influentially connected and occupying an elevated position in his profession should afford no excuse for breaking the law, but rather the contrary.'

Such practitioners ought to be the first to obey and set an example. The patient having stayed at a fashionable hotel makes the offence more grave, as it is unlikely so much care was taken to avoid risk to the other lodgers as would have resulted after inspection by an officer of the local board of health, which was rendered impossible by Dr. Moloney's conduct (The Age, 1889b; The Argus, 1889a).

Moloney will be performing an autopsy on the body of Miss Mary Lyons whose body was found in the scrub. Moloney reports that it is a clear case of violation and murder. The face of the lady was terribly battered, and her body was mutilated. A Javanese man from a nearby camp was suspected. Subsequently Marn, the Javanese charged with the murder of Mary Lynns was acquitted at Cairns after the jury had been locked up all night (The Age, 1894; Ballarat Star, 1894).

Dr. Moloney attended the Rev. Jacob Carroll, who was stabbed on the knee whilst riding in a tramcar. Moloney transferred Carroll to his surgery where he found a wound three-quarters of an inch in length on the knee-cap which he sutured and dressed then splinted the leg. Moloney considered it would have been much worse if the knee joint had been penetrated and expected a full recovery.

The perpetrator, Joel Solomon, was released on bail pending a court case, but subsequently the case was dismissed as an accident occurring when Solomon was cutting tobacco (The Herald, 1894a; 1894b; 1894c)!

Dr Moloney pleaded twice for an adjournment of the insolvency case against Mr Kelly on health grounds. Initially the principal illness which he was suffering from was painful neuritis, or inflammation of the nerves of the shoulder, which prevented him from lying down. Then Kelly developed a new feature, the beginning of dropsy, followed a month later Kelly was confined to his bed suffering from bronchitis and heart disease.

The case was then further adjourned to the 14th August (The Herald, 1894a; The Argus, 1894).

Dr. Moloney appeared as the expert medical witness at the Melbourne County Court before His Honor Judge Walsh on behalf of Mr. Buckler, a retired school teacher. Buckler was walking past the refreshment rooms at Spencer Street railway station when one of the shutters flew open and struck him on the head. Buckland suffered a superficial laceration and concussion with an acute confusional state.

The court returned a verdict against the Railway Commissioners for £250 damages (Great Southern Advocate, 1895).

Dr Moloney was granted six months leave of absence from his position as honorary physician to the Melbourne Hospital (The Herald, 1898).

Conclusion

Moloney gave evidence at thirty seven inquests following deaths from a variety of causes and he performed autopsies on twelve of the bodies. He appeared as an expert witness in court forty one times following a variety of predominantly accidents and assaults, he also appeared once as the plaintiff when he failed to notify a case of typhoid, and once was required to witness an execution. Moloney considered the period required for recovery and the mental trauma in many cases was much greater than the opinion of the defendants doctors.

Moloney was involved in the deaths in hospital of five patients, perhaps from medical misdemeanour or negligence. Mary Glew and Michael Barry suffered respiratory arrests under chloroform anaesthesia perhaps from an excessive dose but the procedures were described as normal and the doctors were not deemed to have been at fault.

Robert Berth suffered a rectal laceration and peritonitis following a difficult peroneal lithotomy for an exceptionally large bladder stone performed by Dr Beaney. It was considered unfortunate and no blame was considered though that the hospital rule of difficult cases being discussed by four hospital surgeons had not been observed and must be in future. A post operative laparotomy may have detected and repaired the rectal perforation.

Mary Moran was dispensed oral carbolic acid erroneously following surgery for a cancer and died. The jury gave a verdict that deceased came suddenly by her death from accidental poisoning by carbolic acid, and expressed deep regret that the dispenser, John Barker, and the wardsman, Humphrey Buckler, were not more careful in obeying the instructions of the resident surgeon.

Anthony Burke died of erysipelas acquired in hospital following admission with a head injury leading to questions about cleanliness and sanitation by the coroner. None would have died had they not been admitted (The Leader, 1868a; Bendigo advertiser, 1871a; Ballarat Courier, 1875; The Age, 1875a; The Argus, 1875a; 1875b; Weekly Times, 1876; The Herald 6/1/1882; The Age, 1882; The Argus, 1882f; 1882g).

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